

Parallel I/O Implementation in Hybrid Molecular Dynamics-Self Consistent Field OCCAM Code using *fpioLib* Library

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Abstract

A new parallel I/O scheme is implemented in the hybrid particle-field MD simulation code called OCCAM. In the new implementation the numbers of input and output files are greatly reduced. Furthermore, the sizes of the input and output files are reduced as the new files are in binary format compared to ASCII files in the original code. The I/O performance is improved due to bulk data transfer instead of small and frequent data transfer in the original code. The results of tests on two different systems show 6-18% performance improvements.

1. Introduction

The OCCAM code is a hybrid particle-field molecular dynamics (MD) simulation code. The main feature of the hybrid particle-field method is that the evaluation of the non-bonded force between different molecules is done by an evaluation of the external potential that depends on the local density obtained in self-consistent field (SCF) simulations. Once the density field has been updated, for every single molecule, no information is needed from other molecules in terms of particle positions. For the calculation of forces due to the interaction of particles with density fields, the only information needed is the density field and its spatial derivatives. These features of the hybrid particle-field formulation, having many non-interacting molecules interacting only with a density field, make this method very suitable for efficiently exploit parallelization. More details about the hybrid particle-field MD-SCF theory and its implementation is described in [1], [2]. In the PRACE preparatory access type C project entitled “Optimization of Hybrid Molecular Dynamics-Self Consistent Field OCCAM CODE” [3], we have worked on the implementation of a parallel I/O scheme in the OCCAM code.

2. Parallelization scheme of OCCAM

The parallelization in the OCCAM code is done by a particle decomposition algorithm. The N particles are distributed over P processors. At each time step, a processor calculates the forces between its particles and those of the rest of the system. Compared to classical MD simulations, in this method, it is not necessary to communicate the positions of all the particles to all the processes, and the only communication operation is related to the update of the density fields. The amount of the communication data in one operation is only related to the number of lattice points where the field is calculated, which is much less than the number of the positions of all particles. In addition, this

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operation is not performed at every time step but according to a prefixed frequency [1], [2]. Due to the low communication overhead, the OCCAM code has very good parallel efficiency over a large number of MPI ranks [1].

To give an example of the scaling behaviour for large-scale simulations, a system composed of 500,000 particles of monoatomic fluid at equilibrium density has been simulated by using both OCCAM and the efficient GROMACS V.4.5. A domain decomposition scheme together with dynamic load balancing for parallel simulations is implemented in the GROMACS 4.5, while the simpler and less efficient atom decomposition is implemented in OCCAM. In Figure 1, benchmarks of MD and MD-SCF simulations are reported.

Figure 1: Benchmarks, measured as steps/s, for MD-SCF simulations (39304 mesh points) performed by using OCCAM and MD simulations. The latter are performed by using GROMACS Ver. 4.5. The system is composed of 500.000 monoatomic fluid water beads (Martini CG model [4]).

As can be seen from Figure 1, the performances of the OCCAM simulations (in which the density field is updated every 100 and 300 steps) are much better than the performances obtained by using a very well optimized MD code such as GROMACS, even if the parallel scheme implemented in OCCAM is less efficient with respect to that one used in GROMACS Ver. 4.5.

3. I/O scheme of the OCCAM code

In the original OCCAM code only serial I/O is implemented. The OCCAM code needs initial coordinates for the molecules. These initial values are stored in the input file. In the pre-processing stage the input file is split into n_p number of files, where n_p is the number of MPI ranks for the OCCAM run. In OCCAM each rank reads input data from its rank specific input file. For output each rank of OCCAM writes to separate files. In a typical run each rank writes 4 different files. Hence, all in all, OCCAM produces $4 \cdot n_p$ output files.

The I/O scheme of the original OCCAM code has some serious drawbacks. Firstly, it needs a large number of input files and also produces a large number of output files. It can become serious problem to manage large numbers of input/output files when trying to run on a large number of MPI ranks.

Furthermore, some systems can put restrictions on how many files can be simultaneously opened. If the OCCAM job hits that limit, then it cannot be run beyond a certain number of ranks.

Secondly, in the OCCAM code read/write is generally scalar read/write. A typical read operation looks like:

```
do i = 1, loop
    read (id, *) x(i), y(i), ...
end do
```

Similarly, a typical write operation looks like:

```
do i = 1, loop
    write (id, *) x(i), y(i), ...
end do
```

As can be seen in the above examples, each I/O call operates on some scalar variables such as the components $x(i)$, $y(i)$, ... etc. of the i^{th} particle's position. This results in many small disk I/O operations. These kind of I/O operations are not optimal for parallel file systems. When all ranks do similar I/O operations on the same file-system, this can become a big bottleneck both for the OCCAM code as well as for the system. A typical OCCAM run, for 500,000 particle system using 128 cores, produces 512 files. The total size of the output files, using a typical writing frequency and 24 h of calculation time, is around 3 GB. For a targeted 100,000,000 particle system running on several thousand MPI ranks, it is expected to generate a huge amount of data. Hence, it is necessary to modify the I/O behaviour of the OCCAM code to cope with the very large data.

4. Parallel I/O scheme for OCCAM

In the project Optimization of Hybrid Molecular Dynamics-Self Consistent Field OCCAM CODE [3], we have developed a new I/O scheme for OCCAM, which is based on a parallel I/O library called *fpioLib*. We have tried to tackle the two bottlenecks of the original I/O scheme of OCCAM code as described in the previous section. In the new scheme, each rank reads from different regions of the same input file. Similarly, each rank writes to the different regions of the same output file. Therefore, the number of files for a OCCAM run is greatly reduced. In addition, in this scheme, the small and frequent I/O is replaced by large buffer I/O in order to reduce the file-system bottleneck. The change from small and frequent I/O to less frequent bulk I/O is achieved via the special interface functions provided in the *fpioLib* library. This has helped us to preserve the structure of the code but still achieving the goal of removing I/O bottlenecks.

5. Description of the *fpioLib* Library

The *fpioLib* is a Fortran library based on MPI I/O. The *fpioLib* is developed while doing the work for the project Optimization of Hybrid Molecular Dynamics-Self Consistent Field OCCAM CODE [3]. It is a standalone separate library that can be used in other applications. In future, the *fpioLib* will be made freely available for incorporating in other applications.

The *fpioLib* is a thin wrapper library around MPI I/O. In MPI I/O read, each rank reads data from different regions of the same file. The read operation is done by `MPI_File_read` or similar routines. Similarly, in MPI I/O write, each rank writes to the different regions of the same file. The write operation is done by `MPI_File_write` or similar routines. These routines are called from all the participating ranks. In MPI I/O, it is very important to specify the relevant locations of the buffers in the file as well as the sizes of the buffers for each rank. This can easily become very complicated where the size of the data is not known a priori. Hence to include MPI I/O natively in an application will require substantial additional book keeping which is both cumbersome and error prone.

The library *fpioLib* gives a much simpler interface for parallel I/O. The buffer location and size calculation is done by the library functions which are transparent to the user. Hence the source code using *fpioLib* remains much cleaner. Also small read / write, e.g., as is used in OCCAM code, is not very suitable for MPI I/O. In MPI I/O large chunks of data should be passed through `MPI_File_read` / `MPI_File_write` routines, otherwise the performance of the code will be impaired. Hence, to do MPI I/O efficiently, the application code should be changed substantially to store variables to some temporary buffer which will be then given to the `MPI_File_read` / `MPI_File_write`. In *fpioLib* this is done internally. For write operations, the data is first stored in an internal buffer, and when a suitably big chunk is stored, the data is written to the file. Similarly, for read operations, first a suitable chunk of data is read and stored in the internal buffer of *fpioLib*, which is subsequently copied to the actual variables. All this is done transparently without changing much of the original code structure.

5.1 Example of *fpioLib* file open/close

In the example below, we will show typical use of *fpioLib* for file opening and closing. We will first show a non-parallel I/O version where each rank is opening and closing a separate file. Here we show only the relevant section:

```
write(str,'(I5.5)') myid           ! my id is the rank
filename = "file-";//trim(str)//".dat"
open (unit=10, file=trim(filename))
close (10)
```

In the above example, rank 0 opens `file-0.dat`, rank 1 opens `file-1.dat` and so on. The parallel I/O version of the above example using *fpioLib* is:

```
call file_dopen(fp0, "file.dat", MPI_MODE_RDONLY, MPI_COMM_WORLD)
call file_dclose(fp0)
```

In the above example, each rank opens the file `file.dat` for parallel reading. The routine `file_dclose` closes the files on each rank.

5.2 Example of *fpioLib* file write

In the example below, we will show a typical use of *fpioLib* for file write. We will first show a non-parallel I/O version where each rank is writing to a separate file. Here we show only the relevant section:

```
write (str,'(I5.5)') myid           ! myid is the rank
filename = "file-";//trim(str)//".dat"
open (unit=10, file=trim(filename))
do j = 1, n
    write (10, *) x(j), n(j)
end do
close (10)
```

In the above example rank 0 writes to `file-0.dat`, rank 1 writes to `file-1.dat` and so on. The parallel I/O version of the above example using *fpioLib* is:

```
call file_dopen(fp,"file.dat",MPI_MODE_WRONLY+MPI_MODE_CREATE,comm)
do j = 1, n
    call file_bwrite(fp, x(j))
    call file_bwrite(fp, n(j))
end do
call file_dwrite(fp)
```

```
call file_dclose(fp)
```

In the above example, a single file called `file.dat` is opened collectively by all ranks. In the write loop, the `file_bwrite` routine is called which actually copies data to an internal buffer connected to the file pointer `fp`. Finally, at the end of the loop, the `file_dwrite` routine is called which writes the data to the disk. The routine `file_dwrite` takes care of the position and size of data from each rank when writing to the file.

5.3 Example of *fpioLib* file read

In the example below, we will show a typical use of *fpioLib* for file read. We will first show a non-parallel I/O version and then the corresponding *fpioLib* based parallel I/O version. In the original version each rank is reading from a separate file. Here we show only the relevant section:

```
write (str,'(I5.5)') myid                               ! myid is the rank
filename = "file-";//trim(str)//".dat"
open (unit=10, file=trim(filename))
do j = 1, n
    read (10, *) x(j), n(j)
end do
close (10)
```

In the above example, rank 0 reads from `file-0.dat`, rank 1 reads from `file-1.dat` and so on. The parallel I/O version of the above example using *fpioLib* is

```
call file_dopen(fp, "file.dat", MPI_MODE_RDONLY, comm)
call file_dread(fp)
do j = 1, n
    call file_bread(fp, x(j))
    call file_bread(fp, n(j))
end do
call file_dclose(fp)
```

In the above example, a single file called `file.dat` is opened collectively by all ranks. The file `file.dat` was previously created by the code shown in the previous section. Before the beginning of the read loop, the `file_dread` routine is called which reads the data from the disk. The routine `file_dread` takes care of the position and size of data for each rank when reading from the file and stores it in the local internal buffer. In the read loop, the `file_bread` routine is called which actually copies data from the internal buffer to the variable.

Once all the data is read into variables another `file_dread` can be called. Each call of `file_dread` reads the amount of data that was written by the corresponding `file_dwrite` routine during the file writing.

As can be seen from the above examples, using *fpioLib* one can easily change a multi-file serial I/O version of a code to a single file parallel I/O version with very little changes. The modified code retains the structure and logic of the code. Furthermore, it is much more efficient than the original example codes shown above as frequent read/write is replaced by bulk read/write.

The `file_bwrite` / `file_bread` routine can handle several Fortran data types, e.g., in the examples above `x(j)` is double precision while `n(j)` is an integer type. At present both `file_bwrite` / `file_bread` support Fortran float, double precision, integer and character data types. Both single values as well as single arrays of these variables are supported. In future, more data types and higher dimensional arrays will be supported.

6. Modification of OCCAM preprocessor code IOPC

Pre-processing for OCCAM input data is done in the IOPC code. In the original IOPC code the main input file is split into `numprocs` number of input files, where `numprocs` is the number of ranks to be used for the OCCAM run. In the modified IOPC code, only one output file is created. Both the original and modified codes are kept in the same source files. In normal compilation of the code, the modified version will be compiled. If the `-DASCII_FILE` pre-processor flag is set in the Makefile, the original code will be compiled. The IOPC code is a serial code. The modified IOPC code is also serial. However, it uses some MPI data structures. Hence, it is compiled with MPI library and is run as a 1 rank MPI job. The two most important changes that are done to the IOPC code are in the file opening and writing sections. We will show below these changes in some detail.

6.1 IOPC output file opening

The file opening code is in the `ofile.F` file in the IOPC code. In the code sample below, we show how the output file opening is implemented in IOPC code:

```
#ifdef ASCII_FILE          ! original section
do id = 1, numprocs
  open (unit=(20+id),status='UNKNOWN',access='SEQUENTIAL',form='FORMATTED')
enddo
#else
      ! modified section
allocate(fp(numprocs))
call file_dopen(fp,"init_bin.dat",MPI_MODE_WRONLY+MPI_MODE_CREATE)
#endif
```

In the above, in the original section the single process opens `numprocs` number of files for writing. The names of these files are `21.fort`, `22.fort` etc. In the modified section a single file “`init_bin.dat`” is opened for writing. The `fp` array in the above code is a data type defined in the *fpioLib* library.

6.2 IOPC output file writing

The output file writing code is in the `wrconf.F` file in the IOPC code. Below we show a typical code section to show how file writing is implemented in both the original as well as the modified code.

```
do i = 1, numprocs
  .....
  do js = 1, molApara(i)
    .....
    do is = 1, npartA
      .....
#ifdef ASCII_FILE          ! original section
  write(20+i,*) vars (is, js, i)
#else
      ! modified section
  call file_bwrite(fp(i), vars (is, js, i))
#endif
    end do
  end do
end do
#ifdef ASCII_FILE          ! modified section
  call file_dwrite(fp)
#endif
```

In the above code example in the original section the variable `vars(is, js, i)` is written to respective files. In the modified section the variable `vars(is, js, i)` is first written to the `fpioLib` internal buffer. This is achieved by the call to `file_bwrite`. Then, finally after the end of the write loop, the whole data is written to the disk by calling `file_dwrite`.

The modified IOPC code runs approximately 2 to 3 times faster than the original IOPC code. As the pre-processing time is not significant compared to overall runtime of OCCAM, this is not critical at present but for very large input files in future, the pre-processing time may be significant and then the modified version can be very useful. The improvement in speed is due to bulk data write in the modified code compared to frequent data write in the original code. The file size on the disk is also much less for the modified code as the data is stored in binary format compared to ASCII format used in the original IOPC code.

7. Modification of the OCCAM code using `fpioLib` library

In the original OCCAM code, each rank reads the input file. The output is written to separate files by each rank. This is a potential bottleneck for the OCCAM code. To remove the bottleneck, we have modified the I/O part of OCCAM to enable parallel I/O. We have kept both the original and modified code in the same source files. In normal compilation of the code, the modified version will be compiled. If the `-DASCII_FILE` pre-processor flag is set in the Makefile, the original code will be compiled. The changes in the OCCAM code are related to file opening, file reading, file writing and file closing sections of the OCCAM code.

7.1 OCCAM file opening

In the OCCAM code, file opening code is in the file `ofiles.F`. In the code sample below, we show how the file opening is implemented:

```
#ifndef ASCII_FILE          ! original code
  io20=myid+21
  open (io20)
  io200=myid+201
  open (io200)
  io400 = myid+401
  open(io400)
  io600 = myid+601
  open(io600)
#else                        ! modified code
  call file_dopen(fp20, "init_bin.dat", MPI_MODE_RDONLY, comm)
  call file_dopen(fp200, "traj", MPI_MODE_WRONLY+MPI_MODE_CREATE, comm)
  call file_dopen(fp400, "conf", MPI_MODE_WRONLY+MPI_MODE_CREATE, comm)
  call file_dopen(fp600, "wvalues", MPI_MODE_WRONLY+MPI_MODE_CREATE, comm)
#endif
```

In the original code, enclosed in the `#ifndef ASCII_FILE` section, rank 0 opens files `21.fort`, `201.fort`, `401.fort` and `601.fort`; rank 1 opens files `22.fort`, `202.fort`, `402.fort` and `602.fort` and so on. The files `21.fort`, `22.fort` etc. are the input files prepared by the IOPC code. The other files are different output files. In the modified code only one file for all ranks is used. The function `file_dopen` opens the files. In the modified code the files names are changed to make it easier to understand. The file `init_bin.dat` is the input file and the other files are the different output files.

7.2 OCCAM file reading

In the OCCAM code, file reading code is in the file `rdconf.F`. In the code sample below, we show a typical read block in `rdconf.F`:

```
#ifndef ASCII_FILE          ! modified code
    call file_dread(fp20)
#endif

do n = 1, nummpi           ! read loop
#ifdef ASCII_FILE          ! original code
    read (io20,*) totalm(n)
    read (io20,*) natmpi(n)
#else                      ! modified code
    call file_bread(fp20, totalm(n))
    call file_bread(fp20, natmpi(n))
#endif
enddo
```

In the original code above the variables `totalm(n)` and `natmpi(n)` are read from the file in a loop. In the original version at every iteration of the loop, two variables are read from file. As every rank is doing similar operations on different files, it results in lots of small I/O operations. In the modified code, first the `file_dread` routine is called from all the ranks. This routine picks up the required chunk of data for each rank from the single input file and stores them in the buffer associated with the file pointer. Then in the read loop, `file_bread` is called which copies the data from the buffer to the variables. As the `file_bread` operates on memory, it is much more efficient than reading from the file.

7.3 OCCAM file writing

In the OCCAM code, file writing code is in the files `wconf.F` and `wvalues.F`. In the code sample below, we show a typical code block for file write in `wconf.F`:

```
do i = 1,50
#ifdef ACSII_FILE          ! original code
    write(io600,*) prepmpi(i)
#else                      ! modified code
    call file_bwrite(fp600, prepmpi(i))
#endif
enddo
#ifdef ACSII_FILE          ! modified code
    call file_dwrite(fp600)
#endif
```

In the above write section of the original OCCAM code, the variable `prepmpi(i)` is written to the file in a loop. Each rank writes to its specific file. This results in lots of small I/O calls on the system. In the modified code the variable `prepmpi(i)` is first written to the internal buffer by the routine `file_bwrite` and then, at the end of the write loop, the routine `file_dwrite` is called which writes the whole data to the disk, collectively by all the ranks to the same file.

7.4 OCCAM file closing

In the OCCAM code, file closing code is in the file `main.F`. In the code sample below, we show the code block for file closing

```

#ifndef ASCII_FILE
                                ! modified code
    call file_dclose(fp20)
    call file_dclose(fp200)
    call file_dclose(fp400)
    call file_dclose(fp600)
#endif

```

As can be seen above for the modified code the files are closed in this section by calling the routine `file_dclose`. This routine collectively closes the file handles for all the ranks.

8. Verification of the modified OCCAM code

For verification of the OCCAM code, we have done some tests. We have first compiled and run the original OCCAM code. Once the run is over we have stored the output files in a separate folder. Next we have run the modified version of the OCCAM code. For the purpose of testing we have written some conversion routines which convert the new output files to the original format. Therefore, a single binary output file written by the modified OCCAM code is converted into np output files, where np is the number of ranks of the OCCAM run. Then, these converted output files are compared with the corresponding output files from the original run. These comparisons showed that the files are identical. Hence we can conclude the modified OCCAM code produces correct result for those tests. We have done these tests on a limited number of cases. A more exhaustive scientific validation is being carried out by the PI of the project. For this purpose, we have also developed some post-processing routines to extract the scientifically meaningful parameters from the binary output files produced by the modified OCCAM code.

9. Results and discussion

The I/O routines of OCCAM have been rewritten to implement the parallel I/O using the interface provided by the `fpioLib` library. Approximately, 5% of the OCCAM code have been rewritten, while the `fpioLib` library is a completely new part of the code.

In order to test and measure the performances of the new parallel I/O implementation, we performed tests on two different systems. The description of the systems is reported in the subsections below. The maximum number of processors we used in the test is 4096. The computer resource used for our tests is a Linux infiniband cluster with Intel Haswell (Intel Xeon E5-2670 @2.6GHz 64-Bit) CPU, 16 cores/node with 64 GB RAM per node (4 GB/core). Network communication InfiniBand QDR 40 Gb/s with a latency of 0.7 microseconds.

9.1 System composition

The systems simulated for the tests are realistic systems of surfactant in water solution. We used a coarse-grained (CG) model with a mapping very close to the atomistic (4:1), in which every effective CG bead corresponds to 4 heavy atoms. More details about the CG models can be found in the references [5-6].

9.1.1 System 1.

The system contains 3,220,208 particles and is composed of 3 different molecule types and 12 different particle types. The box size of the system is: 67.2 x 62.2 x 79.9 nm³, the number of mesh points used in the simulation is 995328 (96x96x108). The density field, used for the calculation of intermolecular interactions, is updated every 100 steps. In Figure 2, the performances measured as 1E⁶ step/day, are reported for the old and new parallel I/O implementation.

Figure 2: Step/day for the system 1 as function of the number of CPUs. The open black circles represent the old I/O implementation, while the fulfilled blue circles represent the new I/O parallel implementation.

9.1.2 System 2.

The system contains 12,880,832 particles and is composed of 3 different molecule types and 12 different particle types. The box size of the system is: 134.4 x 134.4 x 79.9 nm³, the number of mesh point used in the simulation is 3981312 (192x192x108). The density field is updated every 100 steps. In Figure 3, the performances measured as 1E⁶ step/day, are reported for the old and new parallel I/O implementation.

Figure 3: Step/day for the system 2 as function of the number of CPUs. The open black circles represent the old I/O implementation, while the fulfilled blue circles represent the new I/O parallel implementation.

As can be seen from Figure 2 and Figure 3, with the new I/O scheme the performance increases by about 6-18 %. Moreover, the number of files is largely reduced to one for both input and output. Due to the efficiency of the *fpioLib* library, we can easily perform simulations on larger numbers of CPUs and can reduce the time to rebuild the whole trajectory in the post-production.

We would like to include the changes made in the OCCAM code as part of the production version of the OCCAM code. It will require some more effort to completely integrate the code in the production version. We would also continue to develop the *fpioLib*. In future the *fpioLib* will be made open source for using in other applications.

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